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Domenico Scarlatti's Sacred Music

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Although Domenico Scarlatti spent the first half of his career primarily as a church musician – while also composing operas, oratorios, serenatas, and chamber vocal music for secular and clerical patrons – the number of surviving vocal works attributed to him, particularly sacred music, is vastly smaller than that of his extant keyboard sonatas. Any assessment of Domenico's sacred music must therefore include clarifying the status and authorship of the works attributed to him.

The list of sacred works included as an appendix to this chapter differs from those published by Boyd and Pagano and by Fabris.¹ It excludes the double-choir and organ *Laudate pueri* found in *P-Lf* 198/2, partly in Alessandro Scarlatti's hand, of a setting by Antonio Cifra (1584-1629), originally published in Rome in 1610;² it also omits the four-voice *Memento Domine David*, certainly the work of Alessandro Scarlatti, since many independent sources name him as the composer,³ and the *Capriccio fugato a dodici*.⁴ Moreover, it reclassifies the four-voice *Magnificat* in D minor – long considered authentic – as a work of doubtful authorship, for reasons explained below.

The existing sacred works represent only a very small part of what Domenico is presumed to have composed in the genre. The *Indice delle carte di musica esistenti nell'Archivio della Venerabile Cappella Giulia*, compiled by the bass singer Giovanni Trinca between 1769 and

¹ M. Boyd and R. Pagano, 'Scarlatti, (Giuseppe) Domenico' in *Grove Music Online*, 2001, updated and revised 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1093/gmo/9781561592630.article.6002278251>; D. Fabris, 'Scarlatti, (Giuseppe) Domenico' in *MGG Online*, 2016, minor revision 2025, <https://www.mgg-online.com/mgg/stable/536050>.

² In *Vesperae, et Motecta Octonis Vocibus decantanda. Avtore Antonio Ciffra romano in alma aede Lavretana Musicae praefecto. Cum basso ad organum. Opus Nonum* (Rome: Bartolomeo Zannetti, 1610), RISM C 2187.

³ See B. J. Poensgen, 'Die Offiziumscompositionen von Alessandro Scarlatti', unpublished Ph.D. dissertation, Universität Hamburg (2004), vol. 1, pp. 158-60, and vol. 2, pp. 16-17, available at <https://ediss.sub.uni-hamburg.de/handle/ediss/1108>. Both the double-choir and organ *Laudate pueri* and the four-voice *Memento Domine David* are listed as works of doubtful attribution by Boyd and Pagano, as well as by Fabris. G. G. Boymann, *Zum vierstimmigen Memento Domine David: Von Alessandro Scarlatti oder Domenico Scarlatti? Oder von wem?*, *Opicia*, 5 (Frattamaggiore: Istituto di Studi Atellani, 2003), attributes the latter work to Francesco Durante (1684-1755) based on manuscript *I-Nc* Rari 1.6.13/1. However, the autographic nature of this source remains highly uncertain; Poensgen dates it to the second half of the eighteenth century.

⁴ Which only appears in Fabris's list. Regarding this piece – which, in my view, should not be classified as a sacred work, as it appears to be primarily an exercise in counterpoint – see L. Hautus, 'Zu dem Domenico Scarlatti zugeschriebenen *Capriccio fugato a dodici*', *Die Musikforschung*, 24 (1971), 294-95, where its attribution to Domenico Scarlatti is considered doubtful. See also M. Boyd, *Domenico Scarlatti – Master of Music* (London: Weidenfeld & Nicolson, 1986), p. 119.

1770, lists forty-five items under the heading ‘Composizioni del signor Scarlatti’,⁵ which most likely correspond to 123 distinct works, many already missing at the time. It includes seven masses: one titled *Albana* for sixteen voices,⁶ two for eight voices, two ‘pastorali a otto’, and two for four voices, one of which is ‘concertata con pieni’; five graduals with varied scorings; the sequence *Lauda Sion* ‘a otto concertata’; six offertories and eighteen psalm settings for different vocal combinations; three hymn settings; and sixteen sets of five antiphons, along with one set of three, for one or more solo voices and organ.⁷

The *Indice* does not fully account for Domenico’s activity during his occasional service at Santa Maria Maggiore from Christmas 1707 into 1708, nor during his Vatican appointments from mid-November 1713 to late August 1719. The two four-voice settings with ripieno doubling of the *Miserere* in *V-CVbav* Capp.Giulia.V.31, along with the alternating solo and choir strophic setting of the hymn *Iste confessor* for the Common of one Confessor in Capp.Giulia.V.32, are not mentioned there. Of the four extant works preserved in the archive of Santa Maria Maggiore – the four-voice psalm *Nisi quia Dominus* with organ accompaniment,⁸ the unaccompanied four-voice setting of the Corpus Christi hymn *Pange lingua*; the motet setting the Matins antiphon for Corpus Christi, *Cibavit nos Dominus*, with similar scoring; and the four-voice *concertato* Mass in A minor known as ‘La stella’ – only the latter can possibly correspond to the *Indice* entry referring to a ‘Messa a quattro concertata con pieni’, although it must have been originally composed for the Cappella Liberiana.⁹ Likewise, the entry for a ‘Messa a quattro piena’ may hypothetically refer to the

⁵ *V-CVbav* Arch.Cap.S.Pietro, Cappella Giulia, Miscellanea 424, starting on fol. 439r, fully transcribed in G. Rostirolla, *La Cappella Giulia 1513-2013: Cinque secoli di musica sacra in San Pietro*, *Analecta musicologica*, 51 (Kassel: Bärenreiter, 2017), vol. 1, p. 578.

⁶ Most likely dedicated to the Archpriest of St Peter’s Basilica, Cardinal Annibale Albani, nephew of Pope Clement XI. The ‘Messa in 16 v. del Scarlatti detta la Albana’ entered the Archive of the Cappella Giulia on 12 December 1775 in a new copy by Giuseppe Lorenzini (see Rostirolla, *La Cappella Giulia*, vol. 1, pp. 597-98, 687). It had already been recorded as ‘missing’ in the 1770 *Indice* and is apparently now lost.

⁷ The antiphons are consistently referred to as ‘Antifone per’ followed by the name of the feast to which they are assigned, implying a set of five pieces (in three cases, ‘Antifone e Inno’). In one instance, however, it is explicitly stated that the antiphons are the ‘prima, seconda, e terza per Pasqua di Resurrezione’, indicating a set of only three. Examples of such sets by Pietro Paolo Bencini (d. 1755) edited from *V-CVbav* Capp.Giulia.VI.99 can be seen in J. Lionnet (ed.), *La Cappella Giulia. Volume I: I vespri nel XVIII secolo* (Lucca: Libreria musicale italiana, 1995), pp. 72-78.

⁸ Which was likely copied in 1720-21, based on the paper used, and entered the basilica’s archive only in 1747, as part of the estate of Pompeo Cannicciari (1670-1744); see Poensgen, ‘Die Offiziumscompositionen’, vol. 1, pp. 9, 118, 132, and vol. 2, p. 146 for the watermark.

⁹ The fact that Scarlatti did not set the ‘Benedictus’ section in the Sanctus and the ‘Dona nobis pacem’ in the Agnus Dei seems to correspond to a tradition of Santa Maria Maggiore, since other masses by earlier and contemporary composers preserved in the basilica’s archive also omit these sections. Examples close to Domenico include his father’s *Messa breve, e concertata* in E minor (*I-Rsm* 73/1, no date) and *Messa per il Santissimo Natale* in A major (*I-Rsm* 73/14, dated 1707), both composed for the Cappella Liberiana. According to Della Libera, the absence of the ‘Dona nobis pacem’ follows the tradition of San Giovanni in Laterano; see L. Della Libera (ed.), *Masses by Alessandro Scarlatti and Francesco Gasparini: Music from the Basilica of Santa*

G minor unaccompanied four-voice Mass, the *Missa quatuor vocum* also known as the ‘Madrid Mass’, as it is contained in *E-Mp* CTL/102, a choirbook copied in 1754 for the Spanish Royal Chapel in Madrid.

If the ‘Madrid Mass’ indeed dates from Domenico’s Roman period, it may correspond to the Mass mentioned by Mendel and Reißmann, who noted that ‘In Rom komponirte S. mehrere Kirchenmusiken, eine vierstimmige Messe (1712) und ein *Salve Regina* sind bekannt’ (‘In Rome, Scarlatti composed several pieces of church music, [of which] a four-part Mass (1712) and a *Salve Regina* are known’).¹⁰ The latter may well be the *Salve regina* in A minor for soprano, alto, and organ-continuo, whose only known complete source – copied from an earlier, partially extant score and parts – is preserved in Bologna.¹¹

From a letter sent by the alto singer Cinzio Vinchioni (d. 1727) to the composer Giacomo Antonio Perti (1661-1756), we learn that in July 1703, at the initiative of Alessandro Scarlatti, a *Laudate pueri* for contralto solo and other works by Domenico – who was then in Naples – were performed at Santa Maria in Montesanto in Rome during Second Vespers for the Feast of Our Lady of Mount Carmel. Regarding Domenico’s *Laudate*, Vinchioni remarked: ‘per dirla giusta a me non piacque nulla perche non si assuefà con lo stile del padre’ (‘to be frank, I did not like it at all, because it does not conform to the father’s style’).¹² In the 1770 *Indice*, there is an entry for ‘Due Laudate pueri a contralto solo, con pieni’, one of which may be the piece referred to in Vinchioni’s letter.

Domenico Scarlatti also contributed newly composed music for the beatification ceremony of the Jesuit priest Jean-François Régis, which took place at St Peter’s Basilica on 24 May 1716.

Maria Maggiore, Rome, Recent Researches in the Music of the Baroque Era, 137 (Middleton: A-R Editions, 2004), p. xi. Most authors associate Domenico’s works preserved in Santa Maria Maggiore with different occasions in 1708 when he collaborated with his father; see, for example, Poensgen, ‘Die Offiziumskompositionen’, vol. 1, pp. 35-36, 71-72, and 112-19. The possibility that these pieces were not originally composed for the Cappella Liberiana but, as Rostirolla suggests, were performed there during or after Domenico’s service at the Vatican and subsequently remained in the basilica’s archive is unlikely (except, as seen, for the *Nisi quia Dominus*); see Rostirolla, *La Cappella Giulia*, vol. 1, p. 577. This, of course, does not prevent copies of some of them from having been made for the Cappella Giulia.

¹⁰ H. Mendel and A. Reißmann, *Musikalisches Conversations-Lexikon: eine Encyclopädie der gesammten musikalischen Wissenschaften; für gebildete aller Stände*, Band 9 (Berlin: Heimann, 1878), p. 72. Boyd and Pagano, in ‘Scarlatti, (Giuseppe) Domenico’, suggest that the ‘Madrid Mass’ may have been Scarlatti’s contribution to the replenishment of the royal library in Madrid following the fire of 1734.

¹¹ See Boyd, *Domenico Scarlatti*, pp. 114 and 125 for a more cautious approach, particularly with regard to the origin and date of the G minor Mass.

¹² Partial transcription in L. Della Libera, *The Roman Sacred Music of Alessandro Scarlatti* (Abingdon: Routledge, 2022), doc. 20, p. 186. The letter, dated 5 August 1703, still mentions the Magnificat, the last psalm, and the antiphons, but the wording is so confusing that makes it difficult to discern which of these works were by Alessandro and which were by Domenico.

According to the printed *Relazione della Sagra Cerimonia*,¹³ ‘Intervennero poi quattro chori de’ migliori e più rinomati Musici di Roma, distribuiti in due gran palchi’ (‘There then took part four choirs of the best and most renowned musicians of Rome, distributed on two large platforms’). The account further states that ‘nella Messa, come nel Vespro si udirono nuove Composizioni fatte a quest’effeto dallo Scarlatti degnissimo Maestro di Cappella di S. Pietro’ (‘in the Mass, as in the Vespers, new compositions were heard, made for this purpose by Scarlatti, most worthy Chapel Master of St Peter’s), and that ‘l’Inno [*Te Deum laudamus*] con una soavissima melodia di quattro Cori’ (‘the Hymn [*Te Deum laudamus*] with a most gentle melody of four choirs’) was sung after the reading of the proclamation Brief. It also records that the Mass celebrated was the *Os justi*, that is, the one using the formulary of the Common of one Confessor not Bishop.¹⁴ For Vespers – specifically, Second Vespers following Mass – fourteen musicians from outside the Cappella Giulia were engaged (including two violinists and an organist ‘per le sonate’, and a bassist), as recorded in a list of payments signed by Domenico Scarlatti.¹⁵ Since the use of four choirs does not necessarily imply that the music was composed for sixteen voices,¹⁶ some items listed in the *Indice* – particularly the ‘Graduale [*Justus ut palma*] per il Commune de’ Confessori non Pontefici a due soprani, e contralto con pieni’ and the ‘Offertorio *Veritas mea* a quattro pieno’, as well as one of the ‘Due Messe a otto piene’, along with the proper psalm settings – and one extant work – the hymn *Iste confessor* – may have been performed on this occasion.¹⁷

¹³ *Relazione della Sagra Cerimonia, Con cui nella Basilica di S. Pietro si dichiarò ascritto al Catalogo de’ Beati sù in Cielo il Servo di Dio Gian Francesco Regis Sacerdote della Compagnia di Gesù* (Rome: Giorgio Placho, 1716).

¹⁴ The *Relazioni* is partially transcribed in S. N. Prozhoguin, ‘Notizia sulla Messa con *Vespro* e sul *Te Deum* di Domenico Scarlatti eseguiti il 24 maggio del 1716 in San Pietro in Vaticano’, unpublished draft paper (2022), <https://www.academia.edu/93742383>. Prozhoguin concludes that the comparison between the *Relazioni* and the list of payments referred to immediately below ‘allows to establish that Domenico Scarlatti ... contributed to the event with at least three compositions: a *Messa per quattro Cori* (16 vv. and Bc-organ), a *Vespro* associated with the Mass as its second part (probably either for the same ensemble, or for 8 vv., 2 violins, 2 violoni, 1 double bass and organ), and a *Te Deum* (written for an unspecified ensemble)’, a conclusion largely shaped by limited familiarity with Catholic liturgy and an overly literal reading of the documents.

¹⁵ *V-CVbav Arch.Cap.S.Pietro, Cappella Giulia, Giustificazioni* 203, doc. n. 105. Summarised in Rostirolla, *La Cappella Giulia*, vol. 1, p. 574, and transcribed in *Appendice XIV: Musicisti romani e non nelle fonti storiche e archivistiche della Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana (1597–1750). Dalle “Liste” dei musicisti ‘straordinari’ attivi nella Basilica di San Pietro*, p. 237, <https://www.dhi-roma.it/am51-appendici.html>, with a few discrepancies regarding the amounts paid to certain musicians.

¹⁶ On issues of performance practice at St Peter’s in the late seventeenth and early eighteenth century, see, for instance, Lionnet (ed.), *La Cappella Giulia*, pp. xxx-xxxi.

¹⁷ R. Kirkpatrick, *Domenico Scarlatti* (Princeton University Press, 1953), p. 58, hypothesises that the setting of *Iste confessor* was composed for the transferal of the remains of Pope Leo the Great on 11 April 1715, and that it was performed on this occasion during the procession through the streets of Rome, in which the entire Chapter of St Peter and a large number of musicians participated. However, the scoring of the piece makes this unlikely.

In 1717, Domenico was entrusted with composing First Vespers for the Feast of St Cecilia.¹⁸ Again, some of the items in the *Indice* – particularly the appropriate psalm settings and the ‘Antifone per Santa Cecilia’ – may correspond to this commission.

Upon moving to Lisbon, Scarlatti entered a fundamentally different institutional context. Records from his time there – first from 29 November 1719 to mid-April 1724, then again from September (or, at the latest, December) 1725 to early February 1727, with a brief return in the autumn of 1729 – indicate the performance of at least eleven sacred works composed by him.¹⁹ Nine of these, presumably comprising a total of twenty-three individual pieces all scored for eight voices, are mentioned in a ceremonial diary of the Patriarchal Church – the *Breve rezume* – likely referring to the liturgical year 1721-22.²⁰ Listed in chronological order, they include: a complete set of responsories for the Feast of the Conception of the Blessed Virgin Mary; a full setting of the *Te Deum* with plainchant intonation;²¹ a complete set of responsories for Christmas; the motet *Spiritus Sanctus* ‘in the 7th tone’ (A major) for the Octave of Pentecost; the motet *Apparuerunt apostoli* ‘in the 6th tone’ (F major) for the Second Sunday after Pentecost; a Mass ‘in the 5th tone up a step further’ (D major); the sequence *Lauda Sion* ‘in the 8th tone’ (G major) for Corpus Christi; another Mass ‘in the 2nd tone with B flat’ (G minor); and a second setting of the sequence *Lauda Sion* ‘in the 5th tone down a step’ (B-flat major).²²

¹⁸ Della Libera, *The Roman Sacred Music*, p. 144.

¹⁹ On Scarlatti’s Portuguese period, see especially J. P. d’Alvarenga, ‘Domenico Scarlatti in the 1720s: Portugal, Travelling, and the Italianisation of the Portuguese Musical Scene’ in M. Sala and W. D. Sutcliffe (eds.), *Domenico Scarlatti Adventures: Essays to Commemorate the 250th Anniversary of his Death* (Bologna: Ut Orpheus, 2008), pp. 17-68. In a recent article, Giuseppina Raggi – drawing on reports sent from Lisbon by Giuseppe Zignoni to the Holy Roman Emperor Charles VI in Vienna, preserved in the Austrian Haus-, Hof- und Staatsarchiv, Portugal, Karton 6 and Karton 12 – establishes that Domenico Scarlatti was, in fact, in London in the autumn of 1719, and that he took up permanent residence in Lisbon from his arrival on 29 November 1719 until shortly before 18 April 1724, when he departed for Rome via Paris; see G. Raggi, ‘Intrecci teatrali tra Domenico Scarlatti e Filippo Juvarra a Lisbona e a Londra: Nuovi documenti’, *Portuguese Journal of Musicology*, new series, 10/1 (2023), 81-118, <https://doi.org/10.57885/0041.rpmns.10/1.2023>. This partially revises the itineraries and chronology I proposed in ‘Domenico Scarlatti in the 1720s’, cited above, and in J. P. d’Alvarenga, ‘Scarlatti in Portugal’ in M. Kroll (ed.), *The Cambridge Companion to the Harpsichord* (Cambridge University Press, 2019), pp. 201-3. It also implies that Domenico’s visit to Alessandro Scarlatti in Naples must have taken place sometime between late 1724 and early 1725.

²⁰ *Breve rezume de tudo o que se canta en cantochaõ, e canto de orgaõ pellos cantores na Santa Igreja Patriarchal* (Brief summary of all that is sung in plainchant and polyphony by the singers at the Holy Patriarchal Church), P-La Ms. 49-I-59 (full transcription at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17170719>). On the contents of this manuscript, see J. P. d’Alvarenga, ‘“To Make of Lisbon a New Rome”: The Repertory of the Patriarchal Church in the 1720s and 1730s’, *Eighteenth-Century Music*, 8/2 (2011), 179-214, and ‘Corrigendum’, *Eighteenth-Century Music*, 9/2 (2012), 295.

²¹ Performed on three occasions – Matins of the Feast of the Conception, Matins of Christmas, and Matins of the Epiphany – assuming that the references are consistently to the same work.

²² See the transcription of the references to Domenico Scarlatti in the *Breve rezume* and the list of works in Alvarenga, ‘Domenico Scarlatti in the 1720s’, pp. 65-68. In certain cases, correspondences between tones and modern keys differ from those in previous publications, due to further research on the subject.

In addition, accounts from the Nunciature in Lisbon, the representative of the Holy Roman Emperor, and the periodical *Gazeta de Lisboa* provide information about a *Te Deum* by Domenico Scarlatti performed with four choirs at the Jesuit church of St Roch on 31 December 1721.²³ Continuing a tradition established in 1718 for the year-end thanksgiving service, the hymn was likely set for sixteen voices with orchestral accompaniment, its verses alternating with plainchant sung by those in attendance. Since the ceremony also included the Rite of Eucharistic Exposition and Benediction in the manner of Rome, it is probable that settings of *O salutaris hostia*, the *Tantum ergo*, and an opening *sinfonia* were likewise performed alongside the *Te Deum*.²⁴

A report to Emperor Charles VI also mentions ‘una nuova messa da cantarsi a più chori di musici’ (‘a new mass to be sung by several choirs of musicians’), composed by Domenico Scarlatti and performed by all the singers of the Patriarchal Church and the entire court orchestra, for the Feast of St Benedict, celebrated at the monastery of Odivelas and attended incognito by King João V on 8 April 1723, including Matins the day before that lasted for five hours.²⁵

Despite detailed contemporary records, of the works from Domenico’s Portuguese period, only one in the *Breve rezume* can be identified with certainty: the *Te Deum* in C major for eight voices and organ-continuo, preserved in six Portuguese sources, datable to 1721. Additionally, one of the eight-voice settings of *Lauda Sion* cited in the same document may correspond to the ‘Sequenza per il Corpus Domini a otto concertata’ listed in the 1770 *Indice* of the Cappella Giulia.²⁶

It is apparent that Domenico Scarlatti brought with him to Lisbon music he had composed in Rome.²⁷ The existence of a set of parts of the *Miserere* in G minor in the Municipal Library of Elvas (*P-Em* Caixa 377, n.º 17) attests to this. This circumstance could, on the one hand,

²³ See the transcriptions of the relevant reports of the Papal Nuncio and the *Gazeta de Lisboa* in Alvarenga, ‘Domenico Scarlatti in the 1720s’, pp. 59-60. Transcriptions of Giuseppe Zignoni’s reports to Emperor Charles VI mentioning Scarlatti’s *Te Deum* are found in Raggi, ‘Intrecci teatrali’, 106. Excerpts from the Nuncios’ reports in the Archivio Segreto Vaticano, Segreteria di Stato, Portogallo, vols. 65-105, covering the years 1708 to 1750, were first published in G. Doderer and C. R. Fernandes, ‘A música da Sociedade Joanina nos relatórios da Nunciatura Apostólica em Lisboa (1706-1750)’, *Revista Portuguesa de Musicologia*, 3 (1993), 69-146, at 82-146, <https://doi.org/10.57885/rpmns.83>.

²⁴ On general aspects of scoring, structure, and performance practice of the year-end *Te Deum*, see Alvarenga, ‘Domenico Scarlatti in the 1720s’, pp. 62-64.

²⁵ Transcription in Raggi, ‘Intrecci teatrali’, 112-13 (reports dated 6 and 13 April 1723).

²⁶ See the transcription in Rostirolla, *La Cappella Giulia*, vol. 1, p. 578.

²⁷ Presumably along with works by his father – some in autograph form, such as the eight-voice responsory *O magnum mysterium* dated 7 December 1705, preserved in *P-Lf* 197/2, or the four-voice *Miserere* in A minor in *US-BEm* M 2038.A.66, ‘Fatto l’An.º 1721 Copiato per Originale Del Cav.º Aless.º Scarlatti in Lisboa. Die 20. Martio 1721’. On this latter work and its copies, see Poensgen, ‘Die Offiziumskompositionen’, vol. 1, pp. 133-36, and vol. 2, p. 21.

explain the number of works marked as ‘missing’ in the 1770 *Indice* of the Cappella Giulia and, on the other, partly account for the loss of the vast majority of his sacred works, which may have perished in the 1755 Lisbon earthquake. Some may also have been taken to Spain by him or by Infanta Maria Bárbara, most of which subsequently became dispersed or were lost through Farinelli’s estate.²⁸

The description of the contents of Maria Bárbara’s music collection appears in the inventory appended to Farinelli’s will.²⁹ In addition to numerous volumes of sonatas, serenatas, intermezzi, cantatas, and music of unspecified genres, it lists unidentified ‘Musica di Chiesa del Sig.^r Scarlatti, un libro’; the ‘Stabat Mater, Musica del Sig.^r Scarlati, due libri’ (presumably two separate copies); and the ‘Salve Regina di Scarlatti, un libro’.³⁰ Of these items, only one of the books corresponding to the ten-voice *Stabat mater* can be identified with the copy now preserved in *I-Bc* KK.92.³¹ The *Salve regina* is most certainly the cantata-like setting in A major for soprano, strings, and continuo, dated 1756 in the late eighteenth-century copy *I-Nc* Mus.Rel. 3158. It is identified as the ‘ultima delle sue Opere fatta in Madrid poco prima di morire’ (‘last of his works made in Madrid shortly before he died’) in the Santini copies – *D-MÜs* SANT. Hs. 3514 (no. 5) and *RUS-Mk* XI-409 (no. 12)³² – from which all other late extant copies and versions are likely derived. The remaining item may refer either to works composed in Spain or to earlier ones composed in Rome or Lisbon.³³ Of the surviving works, apart from the *Salve regina* in A major (which, despite the date in the Naples copy, may have been composed in the following year, 1757, in light of the note found in Santini’s copies), only one other bears an explicit date. This is the motet for St John the Baptist, *Antra, valles, divo plaudant*, for five voices, strings, and continuo, copied in separate

²⁸ The hypothesis that Domenico left most of his sacred music in Lisbon, or alternatively took it with him to Spain, was already put forward in Kirkpatrick, *Domenico Scarlatti*, pp. 58-59.

²⁹ *I-Bas* Archivio notarile, Lorenzo Gambarini, 1783, maggio 2, segn. 5/14, n° 17 [4660], fols. 122r-143r, partly published in S. Cappelletto, *La voce perduta. Vita di Farinelli e virato cantore* (Turin: EDT, 1995), pp. 211-21, and fully transcribed in S. Erro Saavedra, ‘La música en la Real Cámara durante el reinado de Fernando VI y María Bárbara de Braganza (1746-1759)’, unpublished Doctoral thesis, Universidad Complutense de Madrid (2023), vol. 2, pp. 5-36, with a thorough analysis in vol. 1, pp. 115-76, available at <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.14352/109862>.

³⁰ See Erro Saavedra, ‘La música en la Real Cámara’, vol. 2, pp. 23, 26, and 29.

³¹ See S. N. Prozhoguin, *Indizi codicologici e documentali dei passaggi di proprietà prima del 1835 sui 17 volumi di composizioni di Domenico Scarlatti della Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana di Venezia [BMV] [Allegato (I) alla “Scheda Possessori” dei codici scarlattiani della BNM], Parte I* (latest version 2021), pp. 29-30, available through <https://archiviopossessori.it/archivio/398-barbara>; and Erro Saavedra, ‘La música en la Real Cámara’, vol. 1, pp. 170-71.

³² In the latter source, also in the hand of Fortunato Santini (1778-1861), the note is more precise: ‘ultima delle sue opere (da servire di modello) in Madrid pochi giorni avanti la sua morte’ (‘the last of his works (to serve as an exemplar) in Madrid a few days before his death’).

³³ Among which were perhaps the (lost) settings of *Dixit Dominus* and *Lauda Jerusalem* cited in A. Soler, *Llave de la modulacion, y antiguedades de la musica* (Madrid: Joachin Ibarra, 1672), p. 115.

parts – likely in Domenico’s own hand – in 1701, and certainly composed that year, shortly before his appointment as organist and composer to the Royal Chapel in Naples.³⁴ The piece sets a non-liturgical text in the manner of a *mottettone alla napoletana*, comprising a *concertato* chorus featuring the first soprano, a recitative and aria, a duet, a second recitative and aria, and a *da capo* repetition of the opening movement.

The works preserved in Rome and the Vatican were undoubtedly composed between 1708 and 1719. As noted above, at least one of them – the hymn *Iste confessor* – is circumstantially associated with a specific occasion in 1716. Two others – the hymn *Pange lingua* and the motet *Cibavit nos Dominus* – were almost certainly composed for Corpus Christi in 1708.³⁵ Other works preserved elsewhere may also have a Roman origin. The *Salve regina* in A minor and the *Missa quatuor vocum* in G minor have already been discussed. The former resembles other Roman settings of the same antiphon for two solo voices and organ-continuo, in which the vocal lines proceed primarily in imitation.³⁶ The latter is certainly one of Domenico’s most effective – while somewhat impersonal – achievements in the *stile antico*. Alongside the motet *Cibavit nos Dominus* and the *Miserere* in E minor, it exhibits a well-balanced contrapuntal texture despite relying on a limited set of schemes for developing points of imitation – mostly regularly timed, flexed tonal imitative duos and occasional non-imitative duos – although the *Miserere* in E minor leans towards homophony in some of its verses. The *Miserere* in G minor, in contrast, draws more openly on the *falsobordone* style typical of settings for the Papal Chapels, such as those by Gregorio Allegri (1582-1652) and Tommaso Bai (d. 1714).

Against this Roman repertory, the ten-voice *Stabat mater* occupies a distinctive stylistic and contextual position. The work is commonly associated with Domenico Scarlatti’s Roman period, but this attribution lacks any verifiable evidence and, moreover, does not stylistically align with the pieces securely attributed to him from that time. Based on contextual clues, I have proposed that the work was instead composed in Lisbon in 1721, in connection with a newly instituted *Novena* – a nine-day devotional observance – in honour of Our Lady of Seven Sorrows, which that year commenced on Saturday, 29 March.³⁷

³⁴ See D. Fabris, ‘Una sconosciuta composizione vocale sacra del giovane Domenico Scarlatti per la Cappella Reale di Napoli (1701)’, *Revista Portuguesa de Musicologia*, 7-8 (1997-98), 149-62, <https://doi.org/10.57885/rpmns.158>.

³⁵ Boyd, *Domenico Scarlatti*, p. 115; Poensgen, ‘Die Offiziumskompositionen’, vol. 1, p. 118.

³⁶ Such as, for instance, those composed by Girolamo Chiti (1679-1759) for San Giovanni in Laterano (autographs dated 1717 and 1721 in *I-Rsg* ms. mus. B.1191a-b).

³⁷ Alvarenga, ‘Domenico Scarlatti in the 1720s’, p. 54.

None of the known accounts of the *Novena* name the composer.³⁸ Two copies of the *Stabat mater* were included in Maria Bárbara de Bragança's collection, who, so far as can be ascertained, given the many unidentified pieces, did not possess other works by Domenico not from Lisbon or Spain, except the operas *Tolomeo e Alessandro* and *L'Orlando* (both 1711) and the intermezzo *La Dirindina* (possibly 1715).³⁹ This pattern strongly suggests that the ten-voice *Stabat mater* originated during or after Scarlatti's time in Lisbon.⁴⁰

Another convincing indication of a Lisbon origin for the *Stabat mater* is the prominence of solo passages for the first tenor and second soprano in sections 8, 'Inflammatu', and 10, 'Amen'. At the time, the leading singers in Lisbon were the tenor Gaetano Mossi and the soprano Floriano Flori. In the score of the first part of the serenata *Contesa delle stagioni* (*I-Vnm* Ms. Mus. 9769), premiered on 7 September 1720, a note assigns them the roles of 'Autunno' and 'Primavera', respectively. In the serenata, Mossi's part spans d–bb'', and Flori's d'–a'''. These ranges closely match those of the first tenor (c–ab'') and second soprano (c'–g''') in the *Stabat mater*. Although this correspondence falls within the usual compass of such voice types, it suggests that the vocal writing may have been conceived with these particular singers in mind.

The *Magnificat* in D minor is also generally regarded as having originated in Rome and is attributed to Domenico Scarlatti on the basis of the score in the Santini collection (*D-MÜs* SANT. Hs. 3959) and a secondary source derived from it (*RUS-Mk* XI-408, copied by Fortunato Santini). The first manuscript is in an unknown hand, includes a continuo part added by Santini, and the attribution note – 'Domenico Scarlatti e si crede originale' – is in the hand of Giuseppe Jannacconi (1740-1816). However, an incomplete autograph score by Nicola Fago (1677-1745) also exists, divided between *I-Baf* I-FAG-MUS.1 and *D-B* Mus.ms.autogr. Fago, N. 1 N, and later completed by Gaetano Gaspari (1807-81), presumably based on Fago's now-missing original folios. This version includes two violin parts integral to the texture, and the score indicates that the bass vocal part and the continuo are the same. Other sources that contain only the vocal parts and appear to be related – *GB-Lbl* Add. 14161 and *GB-Ob* MS Tenbury 517 – attribute the work to Fago.

³⁸ The relevant Nunciature report, dated 1 April 1721, is in Alvarenga, 'Domenico Scarlatti in the 1720s', p. 54; Zignoni's account, contained in two letters dated 1 and 8 April 1721, is in Raggi, 'Intrecci teatrali', 103.

³⁹ See the inventory in Erro Saavedra, 'La música en la Real Cámara', vol. 2, pp. 5-36, at pp. 31 and 23, 'Libri differenti', no. [137] and no. [155], and 'Intermezzi', no. 6, respectively. It is possible, however, that some of the fifteen serenatas and six cantatas – unidentified yet attributed to Domenico Scarlatti – also originated in Rome.

⁴⁰ The hypothesis of a Lisbon or Spanish origin is indeed anticipated in M. Marx-Weber, 'Domenico Scarlatti's *Stabat mater*', *Kirchenmusikalisches Jahrbuch*, 71 (1987), 13-22, at 20.

Gilbert Boymann presents an extended argument in favour of Domenico's authorship. However, his reasoning remains ultimately inconclusive concerning the nature of Fago's autograph (despite this composer having demonstrably copied many works by others), and it is clearly biased by his initial assumption that Jannacconi's attribution to Domenico Scarlatti is accurate and reliable.⁴¹ Therefore, also in light of the marked stylistic differences between the *Magnificat* in D minor and Domenico's Roman works in *stile antico*, his authorship of this work must be regarded as highly doubtful.⁴²

The two works preserved exclusively in Portugal in unique sources – the four-voice *pieno* motet *Te gloriosus* in C major with organ-continuo, and the psalm *Laetatus sum* in D major for soprano and alto soli, four-voice choir, and organ-continuo, which are not *stile antico* pieces – do not pose problems of authorship. However, unlike the eight-voice *Te Deum* in C major, no known record of their performance exists, and thus their origin may remain a subject of discussion.

Regarding the first piece, Boyd and Scandrett both draw attention to issues in the final section – the fugato setting 'Beata Trinitas, unus Deus' – notably its disproportionate length, the presence of several parallel fifths and octaves, as well as inconsistencies between the figuring of the organ-continuo part and the harmonies produced by the vocal lines. These features suggest that the organ-continuo part may be a later addition, with the figuring originally referring to the vocal bass part, and that the work itself may date from an earlier period in Domenico's career.⁴³

The second piece is an expansive multi-sectional *concertato* setting that aligns more closely with the descriptions found in the 1770 *Indice* of the Cappella Giulia than with those in the *Breve rezume* of the Lisbon Patriarchal Church for comparable works,⁴⁴ though this

⁴¹ G. G. Boymann, *Zur Autorschaft einiger Chorwerke des Settecento im Stile Antico - Zur Entwicklung eines barocken Personalstils*, Musikwissenschaftliche Reihe 'Genauer betrachtet', 2 (Biedenkopf: Musik Verlag GGB, 2022), pp. 5-62.

⁴² Other works discussed by Boymann – namely, a four-voice setting of *Laetatus sum* in C major, a similar setting of *Beatus vir* in A minor, and a four-voice setting of the *Magnificat* with organ-continuo in D minor (the first two being assigned to Nicola Fago in *GB-Lbl* Add. 14161 and *GB-Ob* MS Tenbury 517, and the third to Pietro Paolo Bencini (d. 1755) in *I-Rn* Mss musicali 20) – are likewise attributed to Domenico Scarlatti, primarily on the assumption that he is the true composer of Fago's *Magnificat* in D minor; see Boymann, *Zur Autorschaft*, pp. 63-96 and 101-12. Nonetheless, as the authorship of this latter piece has not been established beyond doubt, the other pieces should be regarded as the work of the composers to whom they were originally ascribed. The two *Magnificat* settings in C major by Pietro Paolo Bencini, which also appear on RISM as attributed to Domenico Scarlatti – supposedly on Boymann's authority – are, in fact, not discussed by Boymann at all.

⁴³ See Boyd, *Domenico Scarlatti*, p. 122, and R. Scandrett (ed.), *Domenico Scarlatti: Te gloriosus à 4, Motetto in Festo Omnium Sanctorum, Coro à 4 voci SATB e Organo ad libitum* (Stuttgart: Carus-Verlag, 1985), p. 2.

⁴⁴ Most of which are indicated as 'a 8'; however, this may also refer to a four-voice piece performed with a ripieno choir, while only a couple are described as for solo voice and choir.

correspondence does not necessarily imply a Roman origin. In addition to the reuse of the opening material at the beginning of the second part of the lesser doxology – a device employed by Domenico in the *Miserere* in E minor for its final verse⁴⁵ and adopted, more or less consistently, by later composers working at St Peter's in Rome in their psalm settings⁴⁶ – its long first section (comprising psalm verses 1-6 and the first half of verse 7) features a *ritornello*-like structure that further contributes to the overall sense of thematic unity in the piece.

As Boyd has noted, the incomplete 'Messa, à quattro Voci, con Violini, Trombe, Obuè, Timpani, corni dà caccia e Ripieni Del sig^r: Dom:^{co} Scarlatti' (as titled on the part of the 'Organo 2.^o choro') is another imposing, yet concise and extroverted *concertato* work, firmly grounded in its principal key of D major, which allows for the prominent use of trumpets. However, Boyd's assertion that it 'could hardly have been composed for the Basilica Liberiana or St Peter's, nor for the patriarchal chapel in Lisbon'⁴⁷ is likely mistaken. As with the four-voice *concertato* Mass in A minor, the D major Mass omits the 'Benedictus' in the Sanctus and the 'Dona nobis pacem' in the Agnus Dei – a feature typical of Mass settings composed for Santa Maria Maggiore,⁴⁸ but not of those written for St Peter's or the Lisbon Patriarchal Church.

Finally, two previously unknown works attributed to Domenico Scarlatti have recently been identified on the RISM database. These include a setting of Psalm 110, *Confitebor tibi Domine*, in C major for soprano, four-part choir, strings, and organ-continuo, and a second setting of the same psalm in A major with identical scoring.⁴⁹ The record of the latter provides a complete title – 'Confitebor à Canto Precinente è Choro Respondente Violin: 2 Viola. Con Organo Del Sig: Domenico Scarlatti' – and the incipits indicate a multi-sectional structure that, as is apparently usual in Domenico's complete settings, does not correspond to

⁴⁵ Which was rewritten on scraps of paper pasted over the original, though Scarlatti's text remains visible beneath; see the details in M. Marx-Weber, 'Domenico Scarlatti's "Miserere"-Vertonungen für die Cappella Giulia in Rom' in D. Berke and D. Hanemann (eds.), *Alte Musik als ästhetische Gegenwart: Bach, Händel, Schütz. Bericht über den Internationalen Musikwissenschaftlichen Kongress, Stuttgart, 1985* (Kassel: Bärenreiter, 1987), vol. 2, pp. 130-37, at p. 133.

⁴⁶ Niccolò Jommelli (1714-74) being a good example, as ten of his eleven psalm settings from his years at St Peter (1750-54) follow this practice, including the reconstructed *Laudate pueri* for eight soloists, four choirs, and continuo; see A. J. Marques, *Niccolò Jommelli's Laudate Pueri Dominum from Biblioteca Nacional de Portugal for soloists, 4 choirs and basso continuo (Rome 1750): Study, reconstruction and critical edition*, Saggi Ruspoli, 11 (Lucca: Libreria musicale italiana, 2021).

⁴⁷ Boyd, *Domenico Scarlatti*, pp. 126-29; quotation from p. 128.

⁴⁸ See note 9 above.

⁴⁹ Records at <https://rism.online/sources/550268365> and <https://rism.online/sources/550282968>, respectively. The piece corresponding to record <https://rism.online/sources/600033718>, also attributed to Domenico Scarlatti, is in fact a copy or arrangement of Alessandro Scarlatti's first *Missa Clementina* from 1703.

the psalm verses. Structurally, the two settings are largely parallel, differing in only three instances of textual segmentation, with the C-major setting comprising eleven sections, alternating between *concertato* and short solo sections, while the A-major setting appears to consist of only ten sections, according to the available RISM record. In both works, the opening material is reused in the latter half of the lesser doxology, a feature also found in the setting of *Laetatus sum*. Given the similarity of its uncommonly mixed Latin-Italian title – ‘Confitebor à Canto Praecinente Cant: Alt: Ten Basso Violin 2 Viola et Organo Del Sig: Domenico Scarlatti’ – inscribed on the paper cover by the copyist of the parts, the C-major setting likely shares provenance with the A-major one.⁵⁰ Both works were possibly intended for performance in Rome, though neither at Santa Maria Maggiore nor at St Peter’s.⁵¹ Unlike his performance on the keyboard, documented judgments of Domenico Scarlatti’s vocal music are generally unfavourable. As in Vinchioni’s 1703 letter mentioned above, a report by Zignoni concerning a *serenata pastorale* composed by Scarlatti in 1721 and performed again on 7 September 1722 notes that it ‘piace più al Re di quella del Barone di Astorga, ancorchè quelli che intendono il fino della musica stimino questo di gran lunga superiore all’altro nel methodo di comporre’ (‘pleases the King more than that of the Baron of Astorga, although those who understand the purpose of music consider the latter far superior to the former in the method of composing’).⁵² This ‘method of composing’ possibly refers to a certain prolixity (especially apparent in *Laetatus sum*) and to the predictability of its somewhat narrow harmonic vocabulary, in sharp contrast with the boldness of the sonatas – a feature in all of Domenico’s extant sacred music, except the *Stabat mater* and the final *Salve regina*.

⁵⁰ Apart from the information provided on the RISM record, no further details regarding the A-major setting are available, as the holding institution has not granted access to the materials. The C-major setting came from the collection of the composer Josef Antonín Sebling (1710-56), as shown by the inscription ‘Ex rel(iquum) Josephi Antonini Sebling’ in the bottom right corner of the paper covering the parts, already noted in A. Podlaha, *Catalogus collectionis operum artis musicae quae in bibliotheca Capituli Metropolitanii Pragensis asservantur* (Prague Metropolitan Chapter, 1926), p. 49.

⁵¹ Because violas were seldom, if ever, used in the Cappella Liberiana, and the three *Confitebor* settings listed in the 1770 *Indice* of the Cappella Giulia are described as ‘a due, soprano e contralto, con pieni’ (see Rostirolla, *La Cappella Giulia*, vol. 1, p. 578), accompanied only by continuo, as was the practice at St Peter’s. An edition of the *Confitebor* in C major is currently in preparation.

⁵² See the transcription in Raggi, ‘Intrecci teatrali’, 108-9.

Appendix

Domenico Scarlatti's Sacred Music: List of Extant Works

Missa, D major	SATB with ripieno doubling, 2 ob, 2 hn, 2 tpt, timp, 2 vl, org		<i>E-AR</i> Ms. 389 (parts, incomplete, mid-18th c.); <i>E-AR</i> Ms. 388 (reconstructed score, 1754)
Missa breve ('La stella'), A minor	SATB concertato, org		<i>I-Rsm</i> 73/7 (parts, autograph)
Missa quatuor vocum ('Madrid Mass'), G minor	SATB		<i>E-Mp</i> CTL/102 (copy dated 1754, fols. 139v-171r); <i>E-MO</i> Am M.2716
Antra, valles, divo plaudeant, C major	SSATB, 2 vl, vla, bc	1701	<i>I-Nlp</i> Mss. Musicali Di Giacomo K VI 26 (1-2) (parts, possible autograph)
Cibavit nos Dominus, F major	SATB	[1708]	<i>I-Rsm</i> 38/2 h (parts, autograph)
Confitebor (Ps. 110), C major	S, SATB, 2 vl, vla, org		<i>CZ-Pak</i> 1151 (parts, mid-18th c. before 1756)
Iste confessor, G major	S, SATB, org	[1716]	<i>V-CVbav</i> Capp.Giulia.V.32 (parts, before 1719, score and additional parts, mid-19th c.)
Laetatus sum (Ps. 121), D major	S, A, SATB, org		<i>P-VV</i> A.M. B-113.07.pc (parts, mid-18th c.)
Miserere (Ps. 50, odd verses and verse 20), E minor	SATB with ripieno doubling		<i>V-CVbav</i> Capp.Giulia.V.31 (no. 2, parts, before 1719, with later amendments)
Miserere (Ps. 50, odd verses and verse 20), G minor	SATB with ripieno doubling		<i>P-Em</i> Caixa 377 n.º 17 (parts); <i>V-CVbav</i> Capp.Giulia.V.31 (no. 1, parts, autograph)
Nisi quia Dominus (Ps. 123), D minor	SATB, org		<i>I-Rsm</i> 73/8 (parts, 1720-21)
Pange lingua, D minor	SATB	[1708]	<i>I-Rsm</i> 38/2 j (parts, autograph, incomplete: T missing)
Salve regina, A major	S, 2 vl, vla, bc	1756-57	<i>D-B</i> Slg Winterfeld 13 (1) (copy dated 1813); <i>D-HV's</i> No 8 Scar, D/2 (transposed to B-flat major, score and parts, copied 1906); <i>D-HV's</i> No 8 Scar, D/2 b (transposed to C major, score and parts, copied probably in 1915); <i>D-Mbs</i> Coll.mus.Max. 57 (early 19th c.); <i>D-MÚs</i> SANT. Hs. 3514 (no. 5) (1st half of the 19th c.); <i>I-Bc</i> KK.95 (1st half of the 19th c.); <i>I-Nc</i> Mus.Rel. 3158 (dated 1756, copied in the late 18th c.); <i>RUS-Mk</i> XI-409 (no. 12) (copied 1848-53)
Salve regina, A minor	S, A, org		<i>I-Bc</i> KK.93 (two scores, one incomplete, and incomplete voice parts, early 19th c. and earlier)

Stabat mater, C minor	SSSSAATTBB, org	[1721]	<i>A-Wn</i> Mus.Hs.16739 (1st third of the 19th c.); <i>D-B</i> Mb. O. 605 (lost during WW II); <i>D-Mbs</i> Coll.Mus.Max. 66 (1st third of the 19th c.); <i>D-MŮs</i> SANT. Hs. 3961 (1st third of the 19th c.); <i>I-Bc</i> KK.92 (mid-18th c.); <i>I-Vire</i> 152 (formerly in <i>I-Vc</i> , late 18th c.); <i>US-CA</i> MS Mus 22 (short score and parts, 1st half of the 19th c.)
Te Deum, C major	SATB, SATB, org	[1721]	<i>P-EVc</i> Te Deum n.º 32 (parts, 2nd half of the 18th c.); <i>P-G</i> Ms. 92 (parts); <i>P-Ln</i> CN 50 n.º 2 (parts, late 18th c. and later); <i>P-Ln</i> MM 2320 ¹⁻¹⁴ (parts, mid-18th c.); <i>P-Lf</i> 198/3 (parts, mid- to late 18th c.); <i>P-VV</i> A.M. B-113.06.pc + A.M. B.128.05.7.pc (parts, late 18th c. and earlier)
Te gloriosus, C major	SATB, org		<i>P-Lf</i> Ms. 198/1 (parts, 2nd half of the 18th c.)
Doubtful			
Magnificat, D minor	SATB, 2 vl, bc		<i>D-MŮs</i> SANT. Hs. 3959 (1st third of the 18th c.); <i>GB-Lbl</i> Add. 14161 (no. 9) (early 19th c.); <i>GB-Ob</i> MS Tenbury 517 (mid-18th c.); <i>I-Baf</i> I-FAG-MUS.1 + <i>D-B</i> Mus.ms.autogr. Fago, N. 1 N (Fago's truncated autograph score, early 18th c., completed by Gaspari); <i>RUS-Mk</i> XI-408 (no. 6) (copied 1848-53)
Unverified			
Confitebor (Ps. 110), A major	S, SATB, 2 vl, vla, org		<i>CZ-Pkřiž</i> XXXVI B 237 (parts, 2nd quarter of the 18th c.)